

Studies on Succinyl *bis*-N-Phenylhydroxamic Acid as Metal Complexing Ligand

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A number of N-acyl N-phenylhydroxamic acids used as analytical precipitants were known¹⁻³. The interesting results obtained in this field led the present authors to prepare the complexing ligands having two hydroxamic acid residues on both ends of dibasic acyl groups and study their reactions with different metal cations.

With this view succinyl *bis*-N-phenylhydroxamic acid (RH₂) was prepared.

It forms compounds with Cu(II), Fe (III), Al (III), V (V) and U (VI). A tendency of forming long-chain polymeric complexes with this reagent has been noticed.

The magnetic properties of the complex compounds have also been studied. They appear to be high-spin complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of succinyl bis-N-phenylhydroxamic acid: It was prepared by the condensation of succinyl chloride, purified by distillation at low pressure, (3 g.) with recrystallized phenylhydroxylamine (4 g.) in ice-cold ether solution containing 3 g. of dry pyridine⁴. The product was washed with ether, residue agitated with water for 30 minutes, filtered, washed with water and finally recrystallized from hot rectified spirit.

It is insoluble in ether, benzene, petroleum ether, but soluble in ethanol; white shining crystals having m.p. 174°. Found N, 9.28%, C₁₆H₁₆O₄N₂ requires N, 9.33%.

Preparation of Metal Chelates

1. *Copper (II) compound*—To an excess of Cu-acetate in acetone solution, solution of the reagent in rectified spirit was added with stirring. The mixture was warmed on waterbath, when very light greenish yellow precipitate separated. The precipitate was filtered, wash with water to remove excess of Cu-acetate and dried in air. It is greenish yellow powder, insoluble in water. [Found: μ_B =1.88 B.M. Cu, 15.95; N, 7.89. H₂Cu₂R₂ requires Cu, 15.93; N, 7.89%).

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2. Shome, S. C., *Current Science*, 1944, **13**, 257.
3. Shome, S. C., *Analyst.*, 1950, **75**, 27.
4. Lukaschewitch, W.O., *Ann.*, 1936, **521**, 198.

2. *Iron (III) compound*—1.5 g. of the reagent was dissolved in minimum quantity of ethanol and a dilute Fe(III) solution was added to it with thorough stirring (ratio Fe:RH₂—1:2); stirring was continued for further 15 minutes. A red solution was obtained which on dilution with little water formed an orange-red precipitate (pH ~1.5). The precipitate was filtered, washed with cold water and alcohol till free from reactants and dried in air. Colour of the compound is bright orange-red. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol but insoluble in water. [Found: μ_B =5.89 B.M. Fe, 8.24; N, 8.15. Fe(OH)(RH)₂ requires Fe, 8.31; N, 8.34%].

3. *Aluminium compound*:—Aqueous alcoholic solution of Al₂(SO₄)₃, 16H₂O was mixed with the ethanolic solution of the reagent (ratio Al : RH₂=2:3). Alcoholic sodium acetate was added to the mixture to adjust the pH to about 4.5. After warming, the solution was filtered to remove any undissolved matter. The filtrate on keeping for a few days gave a light yellow oily substance, which was insoluble in water, but soluble in alcohol and hardened in air. On crystallisation from dilute alcohol it yielded white crystals. These were washed with water and a little dilute alcohol. It melts at 243° with decomposition. (Found: Al, 5.02; N, 7.68; Al₂R₃, 6.5H₂O requires Al, 5.07; N, 7.88%).

On dehydration at 105-110° it lost in weight and the loss corresponded to 4.5 molecules of water (Loss found 7.46; Calc. for 4.5H₂O, 7.60%). It may therefore be suggested that the original compound was probably Al₂R(RH)₂(OH)₂, 4.5H₂O.

4. *Vanadium (V) compound*—A conc. solution of the reagent in alcohol was mixed with a slight excess of a solution of V₂O₅ in very dilute caustic potash and the mixture was warmed on a water bath when a chocolate precipitate appeared. pH of the solution was found to be 3.0. The precipitate was filtered and recrystallized from alcohol. The compound is diamagnetic. (Found: V, 7.42; N, 7.92. VO(OH)(RH)₂ requires V, 7.47; N, 8.21%).

5. *Uranium (VI) compound*—To an excess of uranyl acetate solution a hot ethanolic solution of the reagent was added and the mixture was stirred thoroughly when a light brownish-red colour developed. By gradual dilution with water the pH was adjusted at 5.0, when a brown precipitate appeared. The precipitate was allowed to settle, filtered, washed with cold rectified spirit and dried in air. (Found: U, 33.15; N, 5.83. (UO₂)₂R(RH)₂ requires U, 33.14; N, 5.85%).

Further work with such reagents is in progress.

The authors express their thanks to Sri R. N. Chakravarty for micro-estimations and one of the authors (D.K.S.) to Dr. S. K. Ghosh, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Chandernagar College, for encouragement.